

Membrane Electrodes

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A membrane is a phase or structure interposed between two phases or compartments which obstructs or completely prevents gross mass movement between the latter, but permits passage with various degrees of restriction of one or several species of particles from the one to the other or between the adjacent phases or compartments, and which thereby acting as a physicochemical machine transforms with various degrees of efficiency according to its nature and the nature and composition of the two adjacent phases or compartments the free energy of the adjacent phases or compartments, or energy applied from the outside to the latter, into other forms of energy^{1,2}.

Membranes while controlling the movements of particles and the flow of energy across their thickness cause a large variety of effects e.g., partial or complete separation of solutes from the solvent, static or dynamic membrane potentials, anomalous osmosis, movements of third ions against concentration gradients, electroosmosis etc.

The thermodynamic relations that form the basis of the theory of membrane equilibria were stated by Gibbs in 1875³. The theory of membrane equilibria was developed by Donnan in 1911⁴. Donnan also obtained an expression for the electric potential difference, commonly known as the 'membrane potential' between two adjacent phases.

The potential usefulness of membrane electrodes was first recognized by Haber⁴ after Nernst and Riesenfeld⁵ had shown that any membrane which in a concentration cell selectively allowed the reversible transfer of only a single ionic species from one solution to the other, gave rise to an electric potential difference (Membrane Potential) and acted electromotively in a manner strictly analogous to a conventional reversible electrode for that ion. Glass electrode which was discovered in the first decade of this century happened to be the first of membrane electrodes where the membrane potential was directly related to the hydrogen ion concentration in solution⁶.

Tendeloo⁷ suggested the use of fluorite, a calcium containing mineral as a suitable selective membrane for the measurement of calcium ion activity. However, actual measurement made by Anderson⁸ revealed non-specificity of aforesaid membranes towards Ca²⁺.

Kolthoff and Sanders⁹ were the first to try coating AgCl onto platinum wires. These electrodes gave poor performances but in recent years, platinum or silver wire coated with polyvinyl chloride having various electroactive materials had been successfully employed in a host of studies¹⁰⁻¹³.

The silicone rubber¹⁴⁻¹⁶ and other polymer based electrodes¹⁷⁻²⁰ that had been satisfactorily tested and used to measure particular ions owe their existence to the earlier works of Tendeloo²¹⁻²³, Marshall²⁴⁻²⁶ and Sollner²⁷⁻²⁹ and to the availability of better polymer materials.

In so far as the development of membrane electrodes is concerned, liquid membranes present an interesting class. Many substances have been used in a pure liquid state and/or in a suitable solvent to form liquid membrane electrodes. These compounds like dinonylnaphthalene sulfonic acid, metal dithizonates etc. do not dissolve in test solution and have the ability to bind certain ions selectively, as a result they behave as ion specific electrodes³⁰⁻³². Some macrocyclic compounds like valinomycin, gramicidin, nonaclins etc. which are electroneutral show good selectivity to certain cations³³⁻³⁹.

Recently electrodes have been invented for sensing gases. Stow and other⁴⁰⁻⁴³ have constructed electrodes for the measurement of partial pressure of carbon dioxide in blood and other fluids. Similarly, other gas sensors have been devised for estimating gases like NH₃, SO₂, NO₂, H₂S, HF etc. These sensors are utilized for various purposes starting from estimations of nitrogen in organic compounds to NO₂ in foods. Ross⁴⁴ has discussed thoroughly the characteristics of air-gap and polymer membranes used to sense gases.

Latest introduction in the array of membrane electrodes are enzyme electrodes. The first enzyme electrode is due to Clark and Lyons⁴⁵ who have estimated glucose amperometrically by means of glucose oxidase placed between two cuprophane membranes. Katz and Rechnitz⁴⁶ have used electrode No. 39/37 for the determination of urea after complete conversion of urea to NH₄⁺ ion by enzymatic hydrolysis. Guilbardt and Hrabankova⁴⁷ have described an electrode using the enzyme L-amino acid oxidase to estimate L-amino acid. Enzyme electrode has been developed to estimate penicillin^{48,49}.

Membrane potential :

The term 'membrane potential' is probably a mixed potential, being a sum of various components. According to Donnan⁵⁰ the expression for the membrane potential, E_M , should be

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{X}{Y} \dots\dots\dots (Eq. 1)$$

where X, Y are concentrations of the co-ions on the two sides of the membrane.

The magnitude and sign of the electric field required to maintain electroneutrality in the case of membranes separating two electrolytic solutions, depends on the nature of the membrane and that of the permeating species. In the case of membranes with fixed charge, the nature of the charge denotes the sign of the potential, whereas the external electrolyte concentration leads to the magnitude of the potential. Though the membranes carrying no charge should have a potential equal to 'liquid junction potential', it was shown by Sollner^{51,52} that many uncharged polymer membranes can be made cation selective⁵³ or anion selective⁵⁴ by making the end and stray functional groups to adsorb large anions or cations respectively.

Without going into details the membrane theories as discussed by Lakshminarayanaiah⁵⁵ following Schlogl⁵⁶ can be grouped as-

- (1) The simple and idealized theory and its refinements ;
- (2) Pseudo-thermodynamic theories ; and
- (3) Theories based on absolute reaction rates.

The theories under categories 1 and 2 have proved useful in the consideration of the membrane electrodes. The theories of Category 3, despite the general and unified view they provide for membrane systems of varying complexities, contain parameters whose physical and/or chemical significance are difficult to understand and whose quantitative evaluation is beyond the usual experimental procedures.

1. The simple and idealized theory (TMS Theory) :

If the membrane is uncharged, the membrane potential will be equivalent to a diffusion potential. As a result, the integrations of the Nernst-Planck flux equation⁵⁷ are those carried out by Planck⁵⁸, Behn⁵⁹, Pleijel⁶⁰, Johnson⁶¹, and Schlogl⁶². On the otherhand, if the membrane is charged, a net Donnan potential in addition to the diffusion potential constitutes the membrane potential. These concepts have been introduced by Teorell⁶³ and Meyer

and Sievers⁶⁴ (TMS theory) and pictorially can be represented as :

Hence, the membrane potential, E_M , becomes,

$$E_M = E'_{Don} + E''_{Don} + E_{Diff} + E_{Ref}$$

where,

E'_{Don} denotes the potential at one side while E''_{Don} of the other. E_{Ref} is the potential due to reference electrode and E_{Diff} is the diffusion potential.

Teorell, Meyer and Sievers evaluated these potentials and obtained the following expression for the potential difference, E_M , between two solutions of a 1 : 1 electrolyte having activities $(a_±)_1$ and $(a_±)_2$.

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} U \ln \frac{X + \bar{U}}{Y + \bar{U}} + \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{Y + 1}{X - 1} \cdot \frac{Y - 1}{X + 1} (Eq. 2).$$

where,

$$X = \sqrt{\frac{4(a_±)_1^2}{A^2} + 1}$$

$$Y = \sqrt{\frac{4(a_±)_2^2}{A^2} + 1}$$

$$\bar{U} = \frac{\bar{U}_c - \bar{U}_a}{\bar{U}_c + \bar{U}_a}$$

where \bar{U}_c and \bar{U}_a denote the individual mobilities of cation and anion respectively in the membrane phase and A =electrical charge of the membrane.

An equation exactly similar to eq. (2) has been derived by Kobatake and coworkers⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷. However, their equation has a parameter ϕX ($0 > \phi > 1$).

the thermodynamically effective charge density in place of A and mobility values corresponding to the bulk aqueous phase in place of \bar{u} i.e.,

$$\bar{u} = (u_+ - u_-) / (u_+ + u_-)$$

Three special cases of eq. 2 are of interest :

(i) when $a \ll A/2$ eq. 2 reduces to the Nernst equation

$$E = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{(a_i)_1}{(a_i)_2} \quad \dots \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

(ii) when $a \gg A/2$, eq. 2 reduced to an equation which gives the value for the diffusion potential between two solutions of activities $(a_i)_1$ and $(a_i)_2$. The mobility values would correspond to those prevailing in the aqueous solution although diffusion would be occurring across the membrane. When $a \gg A/2$ the sorption of the electrolyte by the membrane is so high that the ionogenic groups (i.e. A) in the membrane are unable to distinguish between counter-ions and co-ions.

(iii) when $a \cong A/2$, the ionogenic groups are able to distinguish between counterions and co-ions to some extent so that the mobility values correspond to the membrane phase.

Thus eq. 2 reduces to

$$E = \frac{RT}{F} \frac{\bar{u}_+ - \bar{u}_-}{\bar{u}_+ + \bar{u}_-} \ln \frac{(a_i)_1}{(a_i)_2}$$

or, $E = \frac{RT}{F} (\bar{t}_+ - \bar{t}_-) \ln \frac{(a_i)_1}{(a_i)_2} \quad \dots \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$

where \bar{t}_+ and \bar{t}_- are the transport numbers of counterion and coion for a negatively charged membrane in the membrane phase. Equation (4) may be rearranged to give

$$\frac{E}{E_{\max}} = 2\bar{t}_+ - 1 \quad \text{or} \quad \bar{t}_+ = E / (2E_{\max}) + 0.5 \dots (\text{Eq. 5})$$

where $E_{\max} = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{(a_i)_1}{(a_i)_2}$. Equation (5) has often

been used to calculate the transport numbers in the membrane phase from measurements of membrane potential^{68a,b}.

For many membranes, notably clay^{69,70}, clay-complex, resin complex^{71a}, inorganic precipitates^{71b} and precipitates held on parchment papers⁶⁸, glass membranes^{72,73}, it has been shown that contribution of the diffusion potential is very

small to the overall membrane potential, hence membrane potential becomes only algebraic sum of two Donnan potentials at the interfaces. However, it has been noted that even assumption of a very small fixed charge on the membrane phase is unable to predict theoretically experimental values for membrane potentials when H^+ ion is used as an electrolyte⁶⁹.

It is to be noted that T.M.S. theory does not take into account of (i) solvent transport as well as co-ion transports (for a highly precise work solvent transport cannot be ignored); and (ii) swelling of the membrane which may be unequal on either side due to which a concentration gradient of the fixed charge concentration may arise along the thickness of the membrane phase.

2. Pseudo-thermodynamic theories :

Unlike the TMS theory of membrane potential, which depends on a knowledge of the internal structure and properties of the membrane the thermodynamic theories, as one which has been put forward by Scatchard^{74,75} expressed membrane potential E_m as,

$$E_m = - \frac{RT}{F} \sum_i \int \bar{t}_i d \ln a_i \quad \dots \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

where \bar{t}_i is transport number of i cation of the 1 : 1 electrolyte ij . However, eq. 6 may be applied to all components moving across the membrane. If counterion is considered across a cation exchange membrane then eq. (6) reduces to the famous Nernst equation when $\bar{t}_i = 1$.

Proceeding similarly on the basis of irreversible thermodynamics, Hills, Jacobs and Lakshminarayanaiah⁷⁶, Kobatake⁷⁷ etc. have derived identical relations. Moreover, Lakshminarayanaiah^{78,79,80} has shown that this pseudothermodynamic theory of Scatchard satisfactorily describes the electric potentials arising across membranes when they separate solutions of the same 1 : 1 electrolyte but of different concentrations.

3. Theory based on absolute reaction rates :

This was first suggested by Kobataka and Nagasawa⁸¹ later modified by Nagasawa and Kagawa⁸².

Assuming that a membrane is composed of a number of potential barriers along its thickness they applied Poisson-Boltzmann equation to compute the ionic concentrations in the membrane phase. The

final expression for the membrane potential, E_M is

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \left[\alpha \ln \frac{C_1}{C_2} - \alpha \ln \frac{(C_1 + \beta)}{(C_2 + \beta)} + \frac{\bar{U} - \bar{V}}{\bar{U} + \bar{V}} \ln \frac{(C_1 + \beta)}{(C_2 + \beta)} \right] \dots \text{(Eq. 7)}$$

for 1 : 1 electrolytes :

$$\text{where } \alpha = \frac{K_2(\bar{U} - \bar{V}) + K_3\bar{U}}{K_2(\bar{U} + \bar{V}) + K_3\bar{U}} \text{ and}$$

$$\beta = \frac{K_2(\bar{U} - \bar{V}) + K_3\bar{U}}{K_1(\bar{U} + \bar{V})}$$

K_1 , K_2 and K_3 are complex functions of pore radii in the membrane, electrical potential due to fixed charge and fixed charge concentration of the membrane. According to Tuwiner⁸³ α measures the membrane selectivity for the counterion and β depends on the extent of adsorption of ions by the membrane phase^{71(b)}.

The concentration terms in the above equation when replaced by activity terms, the equation (7) becomes

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \left(\alpha \ln \frac{\bar{a}_+}{\bar{a}_-} - \alpha \ln \frac{(\bar{a}_+ + \beta)}{(\bar{a}_- + \beta)} + \frac{\bar{U} - \bar{V}}{\bar{U} + \bar{V}} \ln \frac{(\bar{a}_+ + \beta)}{(\bar{a}_- + \beta)} \right) \dots \text{(8)}$$

where \bar{a}_+ and \bar{a}_- are ionic activities in the membrane phase and are represented by :

$$\bar{a}_+ = k_{1a} + k_2 + k_3$$

$$\text{and } \bar{a}_- = k_{1a} + k_2$$

When $\alpha = 1$ and β is very small i. e., $\beta \rightarrow 0$, equation (8) reduces to

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} (\bar{t}_+ - \bar{t}_-) \cdot \ln \frac{a_+}{a_-}$$

where $\bar{t}_+ = \frac{\bar{U}}{\bar{U} + \bar{V}}$ and $\bar{t}_- = \frac{\bar{V}}{\bar{U} + \bar{V}}$ are the two

transport numbers in the membrane phase. When the fixed charge is -ve and if it is assumed that $\bar{t}_+ = 1$ and $\bar{t}_- = 0$ (for dilute solutions), the eqn. (8) further reduces to $E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_+}{a_-}$ which is Nernst equation.

The chief limitation of this theory is that its large number of parameters need evaluation and these parameters are different for different membranes. Moreover, the assumption that ' β ' has the same value on the two sides of the membrane, may not be strictly valid⁸⁴.

For many years the only membrane electrode of practical usefulness was the glass electrode until Marshall and collaborators⁸⁵ succeeded in the preparation of clay membranes which, were useful in the determination of the activities of univalent and in some instances of bivalent ions. Mukherjee along with Marshall⁸⁶ used for the first time clay plugs for the determination of activities of alkali and alkaline earth metal ions in electrolytic solutions.

Mitra and Chatterjee prepared clay membranes by careful evaporation at about 80° of 1.5 to 2.0% suspension of less than 0.5 micron fraction of clay, collected from various places of India. The membranes were cut into small discs (about 10 mm in diameter) and heated for 24 to 48 hours at temperatures ranging from 500° to 700° in an electrically heated furnace. These membranes were utilized for measurement of cation activities of various divalent ions in aqueous solutions. The ranges of cation activity over which satisfactory results here obtained, were 0.0001 and 0.0081 for Cu^{+2} , Mn^{+2} and Co^{+2} and 0.0001 and 0.0243 for Zn^{+2} ^{87,88,89}.

Bose developed methods for measurements of individual ion-activity in a mixture of two cations by clay membrane electrodes and extended the same for studying various exchange equilibria in clay sols where clay, resin and glass electrodes were used for measuring ion-activities in a mixture⁹⁰⁻⁹⁵.

Adhikari like earlier workers utilized clay membranes for measurements of activities of a large number of monovalent and divalent ions in aqueous solutions^{96,97}. He attempted to ascertain the role of free sesquioxides of iron and aluminium present in different clays in so far as the electro-chemical behavior of membrane electrodes was concerned⁹⁸.

Adhikari and co-workers later utilised different membrane electrodes prepared from cation and anion exchange resins, and clays for determination of ionic activities of mono and divalent ions in different aquoorganic media⁹⁹⁻¹⁰⁴.

Adhikari and Sen^{105,106} also employed freshly prepared inorganic salt precipitates and various cation complexes embedded on resins or clays for measurement of ionic activities of K^+ , Na^+ , H^+ , Ca^{+2} , Zn^{+2} and Mg^{+2} in different aquo-organic media. However, two decades of study concerning the applicability of estimation of single ion in a mixture of two revealed that measurement of ionic activity of a single ion in a mixture was subject to certain constraints. Adhikari, Ghosh and Modak¹⁰⁷ using clay membranes previously shown by Pain¹⁰⁸ to be more selective towards H^+ ions showed that nature and concentrations of counterions were responsible for variation of selectivity of a clay membrane towards a particular ion. Membrane electrode were used in the determination of the dissociation constants of sulfuric acid¹⁰⁹ and oxalic acid¹¹⁰. Solvation of cations was also determined by using membrane electrodes¹¹¹.

Membrane electrodes have been extensively used in potentiometric titrations^{11,2-115} as indicator electrodes^{6,8,71(b)}, for evaluation of thermodynamic parameters of exchange reactions¹¹⁶, and in determining solubility products¹¹⁷.

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